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Steps to improve the quality and quantity of music education in state schools

June 2025

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Overview

Many of the major policy interventions around music education are predicated on the presence of a sustained music curriculum throughout a young person's life. Music education for most young people is something that takes place in school, through National Curriculum provision, which is a statutory entitlement up to the age of 14. Music should not be an enrichment only activity or framework; it is a fundamental part of a young person's creative development. Without the national curriculum acting as a constant musical thread, available in school, a young person may only experience music education through one-off or short-term opportunities, or may not be able to access music at all. This makes long-term sustained progression all-but impossible for some young people. These opportunities often come at an additional cost, meaning that some young people will not have access simply by virtue of a school having insufficient resources.

The new National Centre for the Arts and Music Education represents a significant opportunity to make positive investments in music education development right across the state sector, but particularly in secondary schools. In this briefing document we outline 3 key issue areas, offering initial proposals for cost-effective and impactful solutions that could be enacted by the new National Centre. Our key recommendations are:

1. **Ensure a sustained and universal music curriculum:** Guarantee a sustained in-school music curriculum as a statutory entitlement for all young people up to the age of 14 in state schools. Operating in an enrichment only space could reduce music education to disconnected one-off or short-term opportunities that fail to offer long-term progression and access, especially for those without additional resources.
2. **Support the availability and uptake of formal music qualifications:** Financially incentivise state schools to offer music qualifications through to the end of Key Stages 4 and 5. This could involve direct encouragement to school leaders, through small subject cost supplements.
 - i. A national 50% subsidy on Level 3 music qualifications entry fees, costing less than £750,000, could support vital progression routes locally.

3. Invest in high-quality, reflective Continuing Professional Development (CPD)

for music teachers: Provide specialised CPD opportunities that enable music teachers to network, explore the intellectual foundations of their practice, and maximize their capacity.

- i. Releasing each secondary music teacher for one day of CPD, an investment of less than £5 million annually, would directly and immediately improve the quality of music education for over 3.2 million secondary school pupils.

4. Address the music teacher recruitment and retention crisis: Implement strategies to bridge the gap between trainee music teachers and Early Career Teachers, given the significant recruitment shortfall (e.g., 59.6% gap for secondary music teachers in 2024-2025), to strengthen the quality pipeline of music educators into schools.

5. Improve data collection for music education quality and impacts: Develop comprehensive and joined up data collection strategies for Music Hubs and schools that move beyond "counting heads". Capturing such qualitative details about the kinds of activities, levels of progression, and frequency of engagement would provide robust quality indicators and return on investment information from Music Education Hub grants and other schemes.

6. Implement targeted investment schemes to address regional and socioeconomic disparities: Develop funding formulae that account for diverse socioeconomic and geographical contexts, moving beyond a per-head basis. This would ensure that Music Education Hubs and schools can leverage additional investment. Such investment can provide tailored provision to all schools, especially those in disadvantaged or rural areas, recognizing the specific challenges faced by a diversity of musical ecosystems.

Quantity and Quality of Music Education in State Schools

1. Introduction

1.1 Many of the major policy interventions around music education are predicated on the presence of a sustained music curriculum throughout a young person's life. However, there is increasing evidence of many schools, particularly at secondary level, where musical experiences are severely limited. Without the national curriculum acting as a constant, a young person may only experience music education through one-off or short-term opportunities, making long-term sustained progression all-but impossible. These opportunities often come at an additional cost, meaning that some young people will not have access simply by virtue of a school having insufficient resources.

1.2 Music education for most young people is something that takes place in school, through National Curriculum provision, which is a statutory entitlement up to the age of 14. School-based music offers a setting where there is, in theory at least, universal access to music education as a discrete curriculum area. This is distinct from, and broader than, simply learning to play a musical instrument, even though this may be an outcome or a supportive activity. As school music offers an essential point of contact and development for all young people in their musicality, it is vital that it is a part of the recognised school curriculum and not annexed into an inaccessible enrichment activity.

2. Mobilising data – School-based Qualifications

2.1 Formal qualifications data at Levels 2 (GCSE equivalent) and 3 (A-level equivalent) are among the most reliable indicators of school music activity. All children have the entitlement to a music education up to the age of 14, which is essential to enabling all young people to access pathways to musical development. Qualification routes need to be available for them as they move beyond 14, to offer further growth opportunities and recognition. However, there are significant disparities in the uptake of music qualifications across different local authorities. For example, in 2024, there were 5 local authorities without a single Level 3 Music entry, including A-level and vocational qualifications. These were Barking and Dagenham, Barnsley, Hartlepool, Knowsley, and South Tyneside. By comparison, there were 378 in Hertfordshire and 321 in Essex. These problems start earlier at Level 2, with Blackpool and Middlesbrough seeing just 35 and 53 entries respectively, compared with 1407 in Hertfordshire. These are long-standing issues, identified in Whittaker et al. 2019.

Related to this, nationwide there has been a marked reduction in the amount of time teachers are spending teaching at Levels 2 and 3. We can take this to mean that there are fewer teachers delivering music education in schools at these higher levels. These low levels of entry at Level 2 and Level 3 show that music qualifications are not available to all young people in all local authorities. Where there are issues in accessing these qualifications in the state sector, young people and their families are forced to either travel great distances to a new school, or enter the independent sector.

2.2 Whilst qualifications do not always mean that music education is taking place in state schools, they are certainly indicators of the likely presence of music in a school. A child cannot choose something that isn't offered. And if there is only one option available, then this might may not be a good fit for their particular musical interests. The absence of mapped progression routes available through all schools is a major impediment to ensuring high quality music education is present in the school lives of all young people.

2.3 *What could be done?*

State schools need to be supported to offer music qualifications right through to the end of Key Stage, even where only small numbers take up these offers. This could come in multiple forms, but direct encouragement to school leaders or a small subject supplement could be transformative. For example, a national 50% subsidy on all Level 3 music qualifications could be delivered for less than £750,000. A targeted investment scheme to help address local authority disparities could achieve significant impacts for schools and young people at a much lower level of funding.

2.4 Such an investment would help support schools to keep small class sizes running and help sustain the vital progression routes that young people are entitled to locally. Without these opportunities, many young people in the state sector, especially those in the most disadvantaged areas, will be prevented from progressing. The impact of this on the school music ecosystem, and on the overall quality of music in a school, cannot be underestimated.

3. Leveraging partnership data – Hubs

3.1 Music Hubs are a leading provider for state schools. Hubs are monitored through an annual return, managed by Arts Council England. This process collects information on the numbers of young people engaged in different activities, including instrumental learning, ensembles, as well as the ways that Hubs engage with schools. The data collected are used in ministerial speeches to talk about how many children are learning to play musical

instruments, or involved in specific musical activities, and are often used as indicators of the quantity and quality of music education in state schools.

3.2 Data shows an overall decrease in the numbers of learners compared with pre-Covid levels, falling from 1,093,512 in 2018/18, to 956,096 in 2022/23). However, the numbers of pupils learning at advanced levels has decreased more sharply over this time (17,618 in 2017/18 [1.6% of all learners], compared with 9,513 in 2022/23 [1%]) (Whittaker, 2023). These data show that Music Hubs engage with around 90% of the schools in their areas, and that around 750,000 children a year (777,809 in 2022/23) have the opportunity to learn a musical instrument through a Whole Class Ensemble Tuition scheme. This is approximately 9.3% of the school-age population.

3.3 *What is missing?*

The current data collection strategies place great reliance on schools and Hubs to collect data themselves, which leads to the counting of heads rather than details as to the kinds of activities. For example, data is collected on the number of 'large orchestras', but there is no way of knowing on a national scale if they are playing at beginner or advanced levels – performing simplified arrangements of 'Twinkle, Twinkle Little Star' or a Beethoven Symphony – or if they rehearse weekly, termly, or more infrequently, or if children continue to play for a long time or stop straight away (Fautley & Whittaker, 2018, p. 37). There is also no easy way to know how this connects to wider school music making or if this is led by a school music teacher, or an external provider. This is a problem because there is an indicator or quantity, but that which is being counted covers a wide spectrum of activity. National data on quantity is limited, and quality is non-existent.

3.4 Similarly, instrumental learning is captured but only in part, with data on external providers being patchy at best. This means that there is only limited knowledge on the numbers of children learning a musical instrument, the levels that they play at, what they are playing, and how many are progressing through state-supported provision or through private means. Such data is vital if we are to understand the return on investment from the Music Education Hub grant.

3.5 *What can be done?*

Existing data does not adequately represent the wider outcomes and benefits of musical participation, or take full quantitative account of the different socioeconomic and geographical contexts of areas. Music education may well improve the life of a young person immeasurably, but they may not choose to attend an ensemble. Based on the dashboard

alone, it would be easy to misunderstand the different challenges that each Hub is addressing. For example, the musical ecosystems of Lincolnshire and Birmingham are very different, leading to enormous discrepancies in the partner investment and income reported. Again, this means that understanding how the MEH grant helps to leverage additional investment cannot be fully understood. This has implications for schools too, as the diversity of provision offered to them by a Hub or the ability to leverage additional investment through a Hub is more restricted. A small rural school 30 miles from the nearest city compared with an inner-city school located close to cultural centres should not have funding allocated simply on a per-head basis.

Data collection needs to reflect the experiences of young people and track impacts on multiple fronts over longer time frames, not just from year to year. This will help evaluate the overall health of local musical ecosystems and criteria that can be used to make strategic investments for maximum impact in a local context. Schools and Hubs should be supported to understand their respective data responsibilities, to establish strong local evidence bases for targeted investments.

4. Access to Continuing Professional Development (CPD)

4.1 Accessing to continuing professional development for music teachers in state schools remains problematic and is critical to the quality of music education schools can offer. This is particularly acute for music teachers as they are often the only classroom teacher in a music department. Our research in Birmingham of secondary schools has found that that from a sample size of 13 schools, the mean number of music teachers per school was 1.3 (Anderson, 2025). Difficulties covering teacher absence during CPD from this critical base, means that music teachers are also less likely to be released from their schools. Music teacher CPD is highly specialised, meaning general school-based CPD offers are less likely to prove effective.

4.2 What can be done?

Reflective CPD, where teachers have opportunities to consider their rationales and the reasons for their curriculum framings, is however, highly impactful. Bridging the gap between trainee music teachers and Early Career Teachers in music is one important focus which could make a real difference to the quality of schools' musical offers. Trainee music teachers are used to having the time and space for reflection on quality music teaching as part of their courses. However, music teacher recruitment is problematic. According DfE figures, the

target for secondary music teachers in 2024-2025 was 820 training places, for which 331 were recruited, leaving a 59.6% gap. The quality pipeline from training into schools is therefore fracturing at a rapid rate. Despite a small increase the 2023-2024 years, the number of music teachers in England is still almost 600 less than in 2012, with a current secondary music teacher workforce of just 7,449. Focused and reflective CPD provision is one effective way to address this gap and to raise the quality of musical experiences for teachers and pupils in schools.

4.3 Such CPD would enable proactive networking amongst the classroom music teaching workforce, thereby avoiding duplication and capitalising on areas of speciality. Reflective CPD maximises music teachers capacity, unleashing their full leadership potential, and develops efficiency. This approach represents compelling value for money, as it is based on enriching teacher practices, and this investment promises significant return on capital outlay. It realises the economics of educational research for a cost-effective educational approach, for targeted music teacher development (DfE, 2025). Off-the-shelf training programmes, which require a uniform application and lack flexibility are unlikely to meet these efficiency criteria or the needs of music teachers, leading to professional frustration and stagnation. There is therefore an opportunity to be grasped in these proposals.

4.4 For less than £5 million a year, each secondary music teacher could be released for one day to undertake CPD. This has the potential to improve the musical lives of over 3.2 million secondary school pupils every year, directly improving the quality of the music education available to all children in school, free at the point of use. This would cost just £1.56 per child. The benefits to staff, students, and the wider music education ecosystem far exceed that cost.

References

Anderson, A. (2025). *Birmingham School Surveys Music Research*.
<https://www.bcu.ac.uk/research/education-and-social-work/birmingham-music-education-bmerg/research-projects/birmingham-school-surveys-music-research>

Department for Education (2025). *Areas of Research Interest*.

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/68136b1bb0ef2c985052541c/DfE_areas_of_research_interest.pdf

Fautley M., and Whittaker, A., (2019) *Key Data on Music Education Hubs 2018*, published by Department for Education and Arts Council England in 2019:

<https://www.artscouncil.org.uk/sites/default/files/download-file/Music%20Education%20Hubs%2C%20Key%20Data%20-%202018.pdf>

Whittaker, A., Fautley, M., Kinsella, V., Anderson, A., (2019) *Geographical and social demographic trends of A-level music students*, published by Royal College of Music, May 2019: [https://www.open-](https://www.open-access.bcu.ac.uk/7511/1/RCM%20RAM%20Report%20FINAL%20180419.pdf)

[access.bcu.ac.uk/7511/1/RCM%20RAM%20Report%20FINAL%20180419.pdf](https://www.open-access.bcu.ac.uk/7511/1/RCM%20RAM%20Report%20FINAL%20180419.pdf)

Whittaker, A., & Fautley, M. (2021). A-level music decline and disadvantage attainment gaps. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655632>

Whittaker, A. (2023). National Plan for Music Education - Getting In and Getting on (APPG Contribution). National Plan for Music Education - All-Party Parliamentary Group Meeting (APPG Music Ed), Parliament and Online. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655534>